

The impact of stress on the health of undergraduate medical students.

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Abstract. In this article we consider the impact of stress on the health of students studying at the Medical University of Samarkand city. Student life in medical universities is characterised by high study load, the need to combine theoretical knowledge with practical skills, as well as constant examinations and assessments, which leads to a significant level of stress. The main purpose of our study is to identify the level of stress among SamSMU students and its relationship with physical and mental health. The study aims to understand how stress affects general well-being and may contribute to the development of various diseases. We conducted a questionnaire among 250 students of Samarkand Medical University. The students completed a questionnaire including the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) to assess stress levels and a questionnaire to identify symptoms of anxiety and depression. We analysed the data using statistical methods. The results showed that 65% of the students had high levels of stress, which was associated with poor health. Students with high stress levels are 40% more likely to report headaches and digestive problems. The level of anxiety among students is 55%, which is significantly higher than in the general population. Thus, the study confirms that high levels of stress negatively affect the health of medical university students, emphasising the need to develop measures to reduce stress and improve the psycho-emotional state of students.

Keywords: Stress, health, students, medical school, psychosomatics, anxiety levels.

Introduction. Student life, especially in medical schools, is associated with high levels of stress due to significant study load, constant examinations and the need to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical skills. These factors create a unique environment in which students are exposed to significant psycho-emotional and physical stress. The term 'stress' was first introduced into scientific usage by Walter Cannon in his writings on the universal 'fight or flight' response. This approach describes how the body responds to a threat. Stress is the body's physiological response to external stimuli and can be described as a state that occurs in response to a perceived threat or challenge. In this context, the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is activated, leading to increased production of cortisol, a stress hormone that plays a key role in the regulation of metabolism, immune function and the response to stressful situations.

Canadian physiologist Hans Selye became one of the most famous researchers of stress. In 1936, he published his first paper on the general adaptation syndrome. For a long time, however, he avoided using the term 'stress' because the term was more often associated with 'neuropsychic' tension. It was not until 1946 that Selye began to actively use the term 'stress' to describe general adaptive stress, which was a significant step in understanding this phenomenon.

Chronic stress resulting from constant pressure can lead to various diseases. According to studies such as the work of B. S. Kobasov (2018), chronic stress is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, gastritis, and mental disorders, including depression and anxiety disorders. Medical students, according to a study conducted by S. V. Maltsev (2020), are more likely to

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experience symptoms of anxiety and depression compared to their peers from other educational institutions. This may be due to the unique demands placed on students in medical schools, where it is necessary not only to assimilate a vast amount of information, but also to apply it in practice. It is important to note that stress is a universal condition to which all people are subject, regardless of their individual characteristics. This makes the topic of stress research particularly relevant, as understanding its mechanisms and consequences can help in developing methods of coping and adapting to stressful situations.

The relevance of the study of the impact of stress on the health of medical students is due to several factors. Firstly, high levels of stress can negatively affect academic performance and quality of learning. Secondly, understanding the impact of stress on students' health can contribute to the development of effective methods of support and prevention, which is especially important in the context of increasing number of students experiencing psycho-emotional disorders. Research shows that students experiencing high levels of stress are more likely to seek medical care and have higher levels of morbidity (I. A. Petrova, 2021). This highlights the need to create programmes aimed at reducing stress, improving psycho-emotional state and supporting students in their academic activities. Among the main causes of stress in students are lack of sleep, work not handed in on time, uncompleted or incorrectly completed assignments, a large number of absences, lack of required work in the discipline, insufficiently complete knowledge of the subject, poor performance in certain disciplines, lack of interest in the subject, increased academic load, conflict situations, poor physical conditions, personal characteristics, etc.

Methods. The object of the study was students of different specialities of Samarkand State Medical University aged from 18 to 23 years old in the number of 250 people. This choice was conditioned by the fact that students of medical specialities often face high levels of stress due to intensive academic workload and emotional demands of the profession.

Subject of the study: causes and manifestations of educational stress.

Research methods: theoretical analysis of information sources, testing, mathematical processing of data.

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) was used. It is designed to assess the level of perceived stress. It includes a series of questions regarding how participants perceive their stressful situations over the past month. The questions cover aspects such as feeling in control of the life situation, frequency of stressful events and general emotions related to stress.

Results. The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is one of the most widely used tools for assessing perceived stress. It includes 10 questions that help determine how stressful participants perceive their lives to be over the past month. It is scored on a 5-point scale, where 0 is 'never' and 4 is 'very often'. As a result of analysing the data from the PSS scale, the following key points were highlighted, the average stress level among the students was 22.5 out of a possible 40 points, indicating a moderately high level of perceived stress (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evaluation of the distribution of scores on the PSS scale.

When questioning students, the main causes of academic stress were identified. Firstly, it is a heavy study load, strict teachers, equally incomprehensible textbooks and irregular meals. The least of all they are concerned about conflicts in the group, problems of cohabitation with other students, conflicts in the group, unwillingness to study. The main factors contributing to students' stress are: high study load, irregular meals, lack of study materials, and excessive use of gadgets. The least anxiety among students is caused by such aspects as problems of cohabitation with fellow students, conflicts in the group, as well as lack of desire to study or disappointment in the chosen profession (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Analysis of factors contributing to learning stress in medical students.

The results obtained from the PSS scale confirm the presence of a high level of perceived stress among medical university students. Moderate and high levels of stress, found in 70% of participants, highlight the need for support programmes and activities aimed at reducing stress and improving the psycho-emotional state of students.

Statistical analysis revealed a significant correlation between stress level and incidence of depression and anxiety. The results showed stress level was positively correlated with symptoms of anxiety ($r =$

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0.65, $p < 0.01$) and also positively correlated with symptoms of depression ($r = 0.70$, $p < 0.01$). These findings indicate that the higher the level of stress, the more often students report symptoms of anxiety and depression.

Discussion. The results of our study confirm the existing hypothesis that high levels of stress among medical university students negatively affect their physical and mental health. The data of the questionnaire survey conducted among 250 students allow us to further understand the mechanisms of stress impact on health and identify potential areas for intervention. According to the data obtained, 70% of students experience high levels of stress. This value is significant and indicates the need for attention to mental health issues in the educational environment. High levels of stress can be due to multiple factors such as intense study load, competition for high grades, and the need to combine theoretical learning with practical skills. These factors create conditions conducive to the development of chronic stress, which in turn can lead to various psychosomatic disorders.

The main findings of the study show that students with high levels of stress are 40 per cent more likely to report headaches and digestive problems. These findings support the theory that stress can cause or exacerbate psychosomatic illnesses. Activation of the GHAD axis during chronic stress leads to increased cortisol production, which can lead to disturbances in various body systems, including cardiovascular and digestive systems. The level of anxiety among students was 55%, which is significantly higher than in the general population. This indicates that medical students are at risk for developing anxiety disorders. High levels of anxiety can hinder the learning process and reduce the overall productivity of students.

Conclusion. The study revealed that an average score of 22.5 out of 40 on the PSS scale indicates a moderately high level of perceived stress among medical university students, which requires attention from the administration of the institution. The identified causes of stress include, heavy study load, strict teachers, incomprehensible textbooks, irregular meals. These factors require the development of targeted support and intervention programmes. Students are least worried about group conflict and cohabitation, which may indicate a more stable social environment in the group. A significant positive correlation between stress levels and symptoms of anxiety ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$) and depression ($r = 0.70$, $p < 0.01$) indicates that high levels of stress contribute to the development of mental health disorders. These results highlight the need to develop and implement psychological support programmes and activities aimed at reducing stress and improving the psycho-emotional state of students.

The results of the study highlight the importance of developing and implementing psychological support and stress management training programmes to improve students' health and their learning process. Creating a supportive educational environment where students can openly discuss their problems and receive help is critical to reducing stress levels and improving overall well-being.

The following methods can be suggested to reduce academic stress:

- Developing study load management programmes
- Psychological support
- Improving access to study materials
- Programmes to improve nutrition
- Managing time and priorities
- Creating a supportive social environment
- Monitoring stress levels

Literature

1. Всемирная организация здравоохранения <https://www.who.int/ru>
2. Бек, А. Т. Cognitive Therapy and the Emotional Disorders. New York: Penguin.
3. Гамильтон, М. The Assessment of Anxiety States by Rating. British Journal of Medical Psychology, 32(1), 50-55.
4. Islomov O. Q. et al. MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN SURGERY //American Journal of Modern World Sciences. – 2025. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 42-48.
5. Nuritdinova P. S., Islomov O. K., Islomova S. X. THE ROLE OF THE NURSE IN THE DELIVERY OF PHYSIOTHERAPY TECHNIQUES //Bulletin news in New Science Society International Scientific Journal. – 2025. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 262-267.
6. Nuritdinova P. S., G'ayrat qizi Xamrayeva S., qizi Eshpulatova D. S. THE ROLE OF THE NURSE IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE PREVENTION //Bulletin news in New Science Society International Scientific Journal. – 2025. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 268-273.
7. Nuritdinova P. S., Klicheva N. K. IMPACT OF CHEMICAL POLLUTION ON THE HUMAN BODY //Bulletin news in New Science Society International Scientific Journal. – 2025. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 218-223.
8. Sharofitdinovna N. P. Shomurotovna RY FARINGIT KASALLIGI HAMDA UNING OLDINI OLISH //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 169-174.
9. Suvankulovich A. K., Musulmanovna S. V. Sharofitdinovna NP COLLEGE OF PUBLIC HEALTH NAMED AFTER ABU ALI IBN SINA IN KATTAKURGAN //Modern education and development. – 2025. – Т. 17. – №. 5. – С. 26-32.
10. Nuritdinova P. S. Features of forming a healthy lifestyle in students //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2023. – Т. 21. – С. 191-193.
11. Nuritdinova P. S., Kushmatova D. E. The role of nursing staff in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of children //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 122-128.
12. Sh P. N. Promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population //Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 1-1 (92). – С. 151-157.
13. Abdug'aprovovna X. N., Maxmudovna H. Y. Sharofitdinovna NP THE ROLE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF THERAPY //Modern education and development. – 2025. – Т. 17. – №. 5. – С. 33-39.
14. Нуритдинова П. Ш., Исломов О. К., қизи Ешпулатова Д. Ш. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЭКСПЕРТА В ОБЛАСТИ ТРАДИЦИОННОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ //American Journal of Modern World Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 243-252.
15. Юлдашева Ш. А., Нуритдинова П. Ш. Экологические проблемы, влияющие на здоровье человека //World of Scientific news in Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 131-136.
16. Sharofitdinovna N. P., Abduroziqovich K. A., Dilovarovna B. J. EMERGENCY CARE ORGANIZATION //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 18-20.
17. Sharofitdinovna N. P., Alamovich K. A., Dilovarovna B. J. ANALYSIS OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 30-33.

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VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

18. Нуритдинова П. Ш., Юлдашева Ш. А. ОСНОВЫ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ КАК КЛЮЧ К ЗДОРОВЬЮ //World of Scientific news in Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 315-320.
19. Nuritdinova P. S., Islomova S. X., qizi Beknazarova D. N. INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OF HEALTH INSURANCE //American Journal of Modern World Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 264-271.
20. Nuritdinova P. S., Yusupov J. O., qizi Omonova M. A. ORGANIZATION OF NURSING CARE FOR PATIENTS WITH INFECTIOUS DISEASES //American Journal of Modern World Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 92-97.
21. Nuritdinova P. S., qizi Ismailova S. S., Baxramova L. X. METHODS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO NURSES STUDYING AT COLLEGE OF PUBLIC HEALTH //American Journal of Modern World Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 165-172.

